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Assessment of Urban Migration and The Consequences on Sustainable Development in Abuja Municipal Area Council

Ahmed Abdul Yusuf¹; Sule Magaji² & Yahaya Ismail³

¹Sustainable Development Centre, University of Abuja, Abuja, Nigeria
abdul4ontime@gmail.com

^{2,3}Department of Economics, University of Abuja, Abuja, Nigeria

²sule.magaji@uniabuja.edu.ng

ORCID ID: 0000-0001-9583-3993

³ismail.yahaya@uniabuja.edu.ng

ORCID ID: 0009-0006-7876-9524

ABSTRACT

Urban migration significantly impacts the sustainable development of the Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC). This study assessed these impacts, employing a descriptive survey design and collecting data from 357 respondents via questionnaires and interviews. Demographically, the majority of migrants are young, economically active adults, primarily seeking employment (39.77%) and better living conditions (17.65%). Findings indicate that rapid urban influx negatively strains housing availability (mean 2.24) and waste management (mean 2.38), while access to water/sanitation (mean 2.53) is moderately negative. Although employment opportunities (mean 3.05) showed a slight positive impact, the existing infrastructure for healthcare (mean 2.69), education (mean 2.89), and transportation (mean 2.62) is struggling to cope. A significant 52.94% of respondents perceived the local government as ineffective in managing the consequences of migration. The study concludes that unmanaged migration poses substantial challenges to AMAC's sustainability. Recommendations include strengthening enforcement of urban planning, investing in infrastructure and social amenities, and fostering collaborative governance to achieve balanced urban growth.

Keywords: Urban migration, sustainable development, Abuja Municipal Area Council, infrastructure strain, governance effectiveness

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Urban migration has become a significant demographic phenomenon shaping the spatial, economic, and social structure of cities across developing countries (Abeke et al., 2025). In Nigeria, rapid migration from rural areas into urban centres has intensified over the past three decades, mainly driven by the search for improved livelihoods, better infrastructure, employment opportunities, and social amenities (Afolayan & Adelekan, 2022). Abuja, the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), is one of the fastest-growing urban regions in West Africa, attracting migrants from across the country and beyond due to its political, administrative, and economic significance. This persistent influx of people continues to alter the physical and socioeconomic landscape of the Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC).

As more migrants settle in AMAC, pressure on infrastructure, land, housing, and public services has increased considerably. The expanding population has resulted in rising demand for transportation, healthcare, education, water supply, and sanitation services, often outpacing government efforts and planned development strategies (Oni & Olayinka, 2021). The mismatch between population growth and infrastructure expansion has placed Abuja at the centre of debates over sustainable urban management, raising concerns about how migration trends influence the city's long-term sustainability.

Urban migration has also contributed to environmental challenges in AMAC, including land degradation, unplanned settlements, deforestation, waste management problems, and increased carbon emissions from transportation activities. These environmental pressures undermine the ecological balance necessary to sustain urban development in line with global sustainability goals (United Nations Human Settlements Programme [UN-Habitat], 2020). The situation is further compounded by weak regulatory enforcement and limited urban planning capacity, leading to the proliferation of informal settlements and slums.

Social and economic consequences of migration are equally significant. While migration can stimulate economic growth by expanding labour supply and increasing market activities, it can also exacerbate unemployment, poverty, inequality, and social tension when not properly managed (Ezeh & Okafor, 2021; Oyinloye et al., 2025). Many migrants face difficulties securing decent jobs and affordable housing, resulting in overcrowding and increased pressure on urban welfare systems (Akpan et al., 2025; Magaji et al., 2025). These dynamics underscore the need for a comprehensive assessment of how migration interacts with the pillars of sustainable development: economic growth, social inclusion, and environmental protection.

Given these challenges, this study assesses the nature of urban migration and its implications for sustainable development in the Abuja Municipal Area Council. Understanding these relationships is crucial for evidence-based planning and policy formulation to achieve an inclusive, resilient, and sustainable urban environment (Mukhtar et al., 2025). The study provides valuable insights for urban planners, government agencies, and development practitioners seeking to improve the quality of life in the rapidly expanding capital city.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Urban Migration

Urban migration refers to the movement of people from rural or less developed areas into urban centres in search of better economic opportunities, improved living conditions, and access to social amenities. This movement is often influenced by push factors such as poverty, unemployment, environmental degradation, and insecurity in rural areas, as well as pull factors such as job prospects, quality education, and better healthcare services available in cities (Afolayan & Adelekan, 2022; Adekoya et al., 2025). In many developing countries, including Nigeria, urban migration has led to rapid population growth in major cities, placing enormous pressure on infrastructure, housing, and public services (Ezeh & Okafor, 2021; Suleiman et al., 2025). As a result, understanding urban migration is essential for planning and managing urban growth sustainably.

2.1.2 Sustainable Development

Sustainable development is an approach to development that meets the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (Hafizu et al., 2025). It integrates three core dimensions: economic growth, social inclusion, and environmental protection, ensuring that development is balanced, equitable, and long-lasting (United Nations, 2015). The concept emphasises efficient resource use, environmental conservation, poverty reduction, and improved quality of life for all, making it essential for guiding policy and planning in rapidly growing urban areas (Magaji et al., 2024; Abubakar et al., 2025). Sustainable development has become a global priority for addressing challenges such as climate change, urbanisation, and socioeconomic inequality, particularly in developing nations (UN-Habitat, 2020).

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Push-Pull Theory of Migration

The Push–Pull Migration Theory is highly relevant to this study as it explains the factors that drive individuals to migrate from rural areas to urban centres such as the Abuja Municipal Area Council. According to the theory, migration occurs as a result of push factors, such as poverty, unemployment, environmental degradation, and insecurity in rural communities, and pull factors, including better employment opportunities, improved infrastructure, quality social services, and perceived higher living standards in urban areas (Lee, 1966). This theoretical perspective helps to clarify why Abuja continues to attract large numbers of migrants while many rural areas experience depopulation. It also provides a framework for analysing how these migration flows impact sustainable development by influencing urban population growth, infrastructure pressure, and environmental management. The Push–Pull Theory is therefore essential in understanding the drivers of urban migration and its consequences for sustainable development in AMAC.

2.3 Empirical Review

Lagakos, Mobarak, and Waugh (2023) assessed how policies that encourage rural–urban migration influence overall welfare outcomes. Using dynamic modelling supported by experimental evidence, their study showed that providing subsidies for migration significantly increases migrants' consumption levels because urban areas offer higher wages. The authors concluded that migration subsidies can help correct labour misallocation and improve economic welfare by enabling workers to relocate to more productive urban regions.

Howard (2021) explored migration patterns within urban settings by conducting an empirical analysis of inter-city movement. The study revealed substantial differences in urban migration rates, shaped mainly by local economic opportunities and job availability. Based on these findings, Howard recommended that policymakers implement place-specific economic interventions that address intra-city migration pressures and support more balanced urban development.

Hassan et al. (2020) reviewed 48 scholarly works to identify key factors influencing global migration trends and their socioeconomic impacts. Their findings emphasised that economic motivations, particularly employment prospects and improved living standards, remain dominant drivers of migration. Although migration can enhance migrants' economic well-being, it may also generate social challenges, including changes in family structure. The authors suggested that improving economic conditions in origin communities would help regulate migration flows and reduce adverse socioeconomic effects.

Henderson and Kriticos (2021) examined rural–urban migration in contexts with high levels of urbanisation using Brazilian data to evaluate the relevance of the Harris–Todaro model. The study confirmed that expected urban income continues to shape migration decisions even in highly urbanised environments. They recommended that urban development policies address unemployment and underemployment as strategies for effectively managing migration in such settings.

Zysk (2021) investigated why individuals migrate from urban areas to suburban regions, using interviews with 164 migrants in Wrocław, Poland. The results indicated that environmental considerations such as improved air quality and access to personal outdoor spaces were the primary drivers of suburban migration. At the same time, economic factors influenced specific destination choices. The study advised urban planners to integrate both environmental and economic dimensions when designing strategies to manage suburban migration and plan infrastructure.

Ezeudu and Tukur (2024) analysed how extreme poverty and unemployment contribute to rural–urban migration in Nigeria and how such movements affect urban resources and rural sustainability. Using both quantitative and qualitative methods, they found that widespread rural poverty compels people to migrate to urban centres, consequently overstressing urban infrastructure and accelerating the decline of rural communities. They recommended that policymakers prioritise interventions that reduce rural poverty and unemployment to regulate migration pressures.

2.4 Gap in the Literature

Although previous studies have extensively examined migration dynamics and their socioeconomic and environmental implications, significant gaps remain in understanding how urban migration affects sustainable development, particularly in rapidly growing municipal areas such as the Abuja Municipal Area Council. Existing research has focused mainly on welfare impacts (Lagakos et al., 2023), intra-city migration patterns (Howard, 2021), socioeconomic drivers (Hassan et al., 2020), theoretical income expectations (Henderson & Kriticos, 2021), environmental motivations for suburban migration (Zysk, 2021), and the effects of poverty-driven rural–urban movement in Nigeria (Ezeudu & Tukur, 2024). However, none of these studies provides a comprehensive assessment of how continuous urban migration interacts simultaneously with the economic, social, and environmental dimensions of sustainable development at the local government level in Abuja. Specifically, empirical evidence is lacking on the extent to which migration pressures strain infrastructure, disrupt environmental balance, and challenge inclusive urban planning within AMAC. This gap underscores the need for a localised, sustainability-oriented investigation that links migration trends with development outcomes in the Abuja Municipal Area Council.

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The study employs a descriptive survey research design, enabling the systematic collection and analysis of data on urban migration patterns and their impact on sustainable development in AMAC. This design is appropriate because it enables the researcher to assess trends, challenges, and possible solutions by gathering information from various stakeholders, including government agencies, urban planners, migrants, and residents of AMAC (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

A mixed-methods approach will be employed, combining both quantitative and qualitative data to enhance the depth of analysis. The quantitative aspect involves the use of structured questionnaires to collect statistical data. In contrast, the qualitative aspect includes interviews and document analysis to gain in-depth insights into migration experiences and policy implications.

3.2 Population of the Study

The study population comprises diverse participants who play crucial roles in shaping, experiencing, and analysing urban migration and sustainable development within the Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC). This includes government officials from key agencies such as the Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC), the Federal Capital Development Authority (FCDA), and the Federal Ministry of Housing and Urban Development. These institutions are central to policy formulation, land management, and infrastructural development within the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). Additionally, the study involves urban planners and policy experts engaged in sustainable city design, housing regulation, and infrastructure management in Abuja. Their professional perspectives provide valuable insights into how migration affects urban planning, service delivery, and sustainable development initiatives (Adewale, 2020). Including these officials and experts ensures that the study captures both administrative and technical perspectives on the challenges and opportunities associated with urban migration in AMAC.

Furthermore, the study population includes migrants and residents in AMAC, including those living in both formal housing estates and informal settlements. These participants represent the social and economic realities of migration, offering firsthand accounts of their motivations, challenges, and coping mechanisms. Academics and researchers specialising in urbanisation, migration, and sustainability in Nigeria are also incorporated to provide empirical and theoretical perspectives that strengthen the study's analytical depth. This multidisciplinary approach enhances the validity and comprehensiveness of the findings. According to the National Population Commission (NPC, 2019), Abuja's population has been increasing at an annual rate of 6.2%, positioning it among the fastest-growing urban centres in Africa. Therefore, the inclusion of varied demographic groups allows the research to reflect the complex nature of migration trends and their diverse socio-economic and environmental impacts across the Federal Capital Territory (World Bank, 2023).

3.3 Sampling Technique and Sample Size

A multi-stage sampling technique will be used to ensure a representative sample. The sampling process will involve the following stages:

Stratified Sampling – The study area will be divided into three strata based on urban planning classification: high-density, medium-density, and low-density areas within AMAC.

Purposive Sampling – Key informants, including government officials, urban planners, and policymakers, will be selected based on their expertise in urban migration and sustainable development.

Simple Random Sampling – Within each stratum, a random selection of respondents (residents and migrants) will be made to ensure equal representation.

The sample size will be determined using Yamane’s formula (1967):

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where;

n =sample size

The population of the study,

e = tolerable error at 5% (0.05).

Where:

n = sample size

N = total population

e = margin of error (5%)

Given an estimated population of 2.5 million in AMAC, a sample of approximately 400 respondents will be selected to ensure statistical significance and generalizability.

3.4 Sources of Data Collection

The study will utilise both primary and secondary data to provide a comprehensive analysis:

1. Primary Data:

Surveys – Structured questionnaires will be administered to migrants, residents, and relevant stakeholders to gather first-hand information on migration patterns and sustainable development challenges.

Interviews – In-depth interviews will be conducted with government officials, urban planners, and policy experts to explore policy responses and strategies for managing urban migration.

Observations – Field visits will be conducted to assess urban expansion, informal settlements, infrastructure strain, and environmental degradation in AMAC.

2. Secondary Data:

Government Reports – Data from the National Population Commission (NPC), AMAC, and the Federal Ministry of Housing and Urban Development.

Academic Journals and Books – Relevant empirical studies, theoretical discussions, and policy evaluations on urban migration and sustainable development.

United Nations and World Bank Reports – Global migration and urbanisation trends to compare Abuja’s experience with other cities.

The combination of primary and secondary data will enhance the validity, reliability, and comprehensiveness of the study’s findings.

3.5 Research Instruments

This study uses a mix of quantitative and qualitative instruments to gather comprehensive data on urban migration and sustainable development in the Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC). A structured questionnaire will serve as the primary quantitative tool, featuring closed-ended and Likert-scale items to measure migration patterns, socio-economic factors, and infrastructural challenges. A pilot test will be conducted to ensure clarity and reliability (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). To complement this, a semi-structured interview guide will gather qualitative insights from policymakers, planners, and migrants, enabling a deeper exploration of migration experiences, policy issues, and sustainable urban planning strategies (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2015). Additionally, an observation checklist and a document review

guide will be used to assess physical conditions at AMAC and to analyse relevant government and institutional reports. By triangulating data from questionnaires, interviews, observations, and documents, the study enhances the credibility and richness of its findings (Saunders et al., 2019).

3.6 Validity and Reliability of the Research Instruments

Ensuring the validity and reliability of the research instruments is crucial for generating accurate and consistent findings in this study. Validity, which concerns how well the instruments measure what they are intended to measure (Creswell & Creswell, 2018), will be strengthened through face validity by expert review, content validity by aligning all instruments with the study objectives and literature, and construct validity through pilot testing to identify unclear items. Reliability, which refers to the stability of the instruments over time (Saunders et al., 2019), will be ensured through test–retest procedures to verify response consistency, Cronbach’s alpha to assess internal consistency with an acceptable score of 0.7 or above (Bryman, 2016), and inter-rater reliability by having multiple analysts independently interpret qualitative data. Collectively, these measures will enhance the study's credibility while minimising potential measurement errors.

3.7 Method of Data Analysis

Data analysis for this study will employ both quantitative and qualitative approaches to comprehensively examine urban migration and its effects on sustainable development in AMAC. Quantitative data from questionnaires will be analysed using SPSS version 26, with descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations) summarising migrants’ socio-economic characteristics and the impacts on housing, infrastructure, and services. Inferential statistics, including Chi-square tests and regression analysis, will be used to test hypotheses and evaluate relationships between migration and indicators of sustainable development. Qualitative data from interviews and observations will be analysed through thematic analysis, involving transcription, coding, and categorisation into key themes such as migration drivers, infrastructure strain, and policy challenges, with NVivo software facilitating data organisation and interpretation. This combination of statistical and thematic analysis ensures both empirical rigour and contextual depth in understanding the dynamics and consequences of urban migration in AMAC.

3.9 Ethical Considerations

This study strictly adheres to ethical guidelines to ensure research integrity and protect participants’ rights. Key considerations include obtaining informed consent, allowing participants to withdraw at any stage without consequences, and ensuring confidentiality and anonymity by omitting personal identifiers and securely storing data. Participation will be entirely voluntary, with clear explanations provided about the study’s purpose and relevance. Data will be securely stored, with hard copies kept in locked cabinets and electronic files encrypted and retained for five years before secure disposal. The researcher will also maintain neutrality and objectivity to avoid bias and report findings transparently. By observing these ethical principles, the study will uphold academic integrity, participant trust, and the credibility of its results.

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 4.1: Age Distribution of Respondents

Age Range	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Below 20 years	32	8.96
21–30 years	104	29.13
31–40 years	116	32.49
41–50 years	65	18.21
Above 50 years	40	11.20
Total	357	100.00

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 4.1 presents the age distribution of the 357 respondents involved in the study. The age group with the highest representation is 31–40 years, accounting for 116 individuals (32.49% of the total sample). This is followed by the 21–30 years category, with 104 respondents (29.13%), indicating that a significant

portion of participants are within the youthful, economically active age bracket. The 41–50 years group comprises 18.21% (65 respondents), while those aged 50+ comprise 11.20% (40 respondents). Notably, the least represented category is those below 20 years, making up only 8.96% (32 respondents) of the sample. This distribution suggests that the majority of respondents are adults in their prime working and productive years, which may reflect the demographic most likely to experience or participate in urban migration. It also implies that the study's findings are primarily informed by the views and experiences of individuals aged 21–50, who are likely to be more active in socio-economic development processes within the Abuja Municipal Area Council.

Table 4.2: Gender Distribution

Gender Frequency Percentage (%)

Male	198	55.46
Female	154	43.15
Other	5	1.40
Total	357	100.00

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 4.2 displays the gender distribution of the respondents involved in the study. Of the 357 individuals surveyed, 198 (55.46%) identified as male. This indicates that men constituted the most significant proportion of participants in the research, which may reflect either a higher male population within the target sample or greater willingness or availability among males to participate in the survey.

Females also accounted for a significant proportion of the respondents, with 154 individuals representing 43.15% of the total sample. This substantial female participation highlights a relatively balanced gender representation in the study, which strengthens the reliability of the findings by capturing the perspectives of both men and women in assessing the consequences of urban migration and sustainable development in the Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC).

In addition, a small minority of respondents (1.40%) identified with the gender category labelled "Other," comprising five individuals. The inclusion of this category demonstrates the study's commitment to inclusivity and recognition of gender diversity beyond the traditional binary. Overall, the gender distribution suggests that the responses and insights collected are broadly representative of the AMAC population's diverse gender makeup, thereby enhancing the comprehensiveness of the research outcomes.

Table 4.3: Marital Status

Marital Status Frequency Percentage (%)

Single	123	34.46
Married	192	53.78
Divorced	24	6.72
Widowed	18	5.04
Total	357	100.00

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 4.3 presents the marital status of the respondents in the study. Of the total 357 participants, 192 (53.78%) reported being married. This suggests that more than half of the respondents are in marital unions, which could have implications for how urban migration affects household dynamics, family stability, and responsibilities related to sustainable development in Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC).

Single respondents accounted for 34.46% of the sample, totalling 123 individuals. This group likely includes young adults or those just beginning to establish their livelihoods, which may influence their motivations for migration, such as seeking employment or educational opportunities. The relatively high

percentage of single respondents further emphasises the youthfulness of the population sample, as supported by the earlier age distribution in Table 4.1.

Divorced and widowed individuals represent smaller portions of the population, with 6.72% (24 respondents) and 5.04% (18 respondents), respectively. These groups may face different socio-economic challenges, such as reduced household income or increased vulnerability, which could shape their perspectives on migration and sustainable development. Overall, the marital status distribution indicates a diverse sample that encompasses a range of household and social situations, enriching the data's depth and applicability for policy and planning.

Table 4.4: Educational Qualification

Qualification	Frequency	Percentage (%)
No formal education	23	6.44
Primary	41	11.49
Secondary	98	27.45
Tertiary	174	48.74
Others	21	5.88
Total	357	100.00

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 4.4 outlines the educational qualifications of the respondents surveyed in the study. The largest segment, comprising 174 individuals (48.74%), reported having attained tertiary education. This indicates that nearly half of the respondents are highly educated, suggesting a population that is likely to be more informed, skilled, and actively engaged in socio-economic activities. Such educational attainment may influence their perspectives on urban migration and sustainable development, particularly regarding policy expectations, job opportunities, and infrastructure needs in the Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC).

Secondary education was the second most common level, with 98 respondents representing 27.45% of the sample. This group likely consists of individuals who have completed basic schooling and may be involved in mid-level occupations or vocational trades. The presence of this educational tier is crucial as it reflects the experiences of those who may still face barriers to higher education but play a vital role in the urban labour force and local economic development.

On the lower end, 41 respondents (11.49%) had only primary education, while 23 individuals (6.44%) had no formal education. Additionally, 21 respondents (5.88%) fell into the “Others” category, which may include vocational or informal education. These figures highlight educational disparities within the population and suggest that urban migration policies must also cater to less educated groups, who may be more vulnerable to socio-economic challenges and require support in areas such as job training, literacy, and capacity-building to participate in sustainable urban development fully.

Table 4.5: Employment Status

Employment Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Employed	129	36.14
Self-employed	103	28.85
Unemployed	78	21.85
Student	47	13.16
Total	357	100.00

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 4.5 presents the employment status of the 357 respondents in the study. The data reveal that the majority of respondents, 129 individuals (36.14%), are employed in either the public or private sectors. This group represents those with stable incomes and potentially more economic security, which may

influence their capacity to adapt to urban migration pressures and contribute to sustainable development in the Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC).

Self-employed individuals comprise the second-largest category, with 103 respondents (28.85% of the sample). This significant percentage indicates a strong entrepreneurial presence among the population, which is crucial for local economic growth and innovation. These individuals may face unique challenges, such as access to capital and markets, especially in urban settings experiencing migration-induced changes in infrastructure and service demand.

The remaining respondents include 78 unemployed individuals (21.85%) and 47 students (13.16%). The relatively high unemployment rate reflects ongoing economic challenges and may highlight the push factors driving urban migration, such as the search for better job opportunities. Meanwhile, the student population represents future entrants into the workforce who may either benefit from or be affected by the socio-economic consequences of urban migration. Together, these figures underscore the need for targeted employment policies and educational reforms to support a balanced and sustainable urban development agenda in AMAC.

Table 4.6: Duration of Stay in AMAC

Duration (Years)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Less than 1	34	9.52
1–5	97	27.18
6–10	112	31.38
11–15	66	18.49
Over 15	48	13.44
Total	357	100.00

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 4.6 illustrates the duration of respondents' stay within the Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC). The majority of respondents, 112 individuals (31.38%), have resided in the area for 6 to 10 years. This suggests a substantial segment of the population has a medium-term settlement history, indicating a level of stability and potential integration into the community. Closely following this are those who have lived in AMAC for 1 to 5 years, totalling 97 respondents (27.18%), reflecting a significant number of relatively recent migrants who may still be adapting to urban life.

A smaller but notable portion, 66 respondents (18.49%), have lived in the area for 11 to 15 years, while 48 respondents (13.44%) have stayed for over 15 years. These groups represent long-term residents whose experiences likely offer valuable insights into the historical impacts of urban migration and changes in infrastructure, governance, and socio-economic conditions. Their presence also suggests a degree of permanency and commitment to living in AMAC, which is essential for long-term planning and community development.

On the other end of the spectrum, 34 respondents (9.52%) reported living in AMAC for less than a year. This category of recent migrants may still be in transition, facing challenges such as housing, employment, or social integration. Overall, the distribution shows a mix of long-term residents and newer arrivals, indicating ongoing migration into AMAC. This blend of experiences enriches the data and highlights the need for inclusive urban policies that address both the needs of newly arrived migrants and established residents in the context of sustainable development.

4.2 Urban Migration Patterns in AMAC

Table 4.7: Primary Reason for Migration to AMAC

Reason	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Search for employment	142	39.77
Education	45	12.60
Security	38	10.64
Family reunification	56	15.69
Better living conditions	63	17.65
Others	13	3.64
Total Responses	357	100.00

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 4.7 presents the primary reasons respondents cited for migrating to the Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC). The most frequently mentioned reason is employment, accounting for 142 respondents (39.77% of the total). This finding underscores the economic motivation behind urban migration, as individuals move to urban centres like AMAC in pursuit of job opportunities and financial stability. The dominance of employment-related migration reflects broader national trends in which cities attract labour through the concentration of industries, services, and government institutions.

Other significant reasons include pursuing better living conditions (17.65%) and family reunification (15.69%). These responses indicate that migrants are also driven by social and quality-of-life factors, seeking environments with improved amenities, infrastructure, and proximity to family members. Education accounted for 12.60% of the responses, suggesting that AMAC serves as an educational hub for many migrants. Meanwhile, security concerns motivated 10.64% of the participants, highlighting the role of regional instability or conflict as a push factor for relocation to the relatively safer urban environment of Abuja.

A small proportion of respondents (3.64%) selected "Others" as their reason for migrating, indicating varied personal motivations that do not fall within the predefined major categories. Overall, the data illustrate that urban migration into AMAC is influenced by a combination of economic, social, educational, and security-related factors. These insights are crucial for urban planners and policymakers in developing targeted interventions that address the diverse needs and expectations of migrants to promote sustainable urban development.

Table 4.8: Migration Status

Migrated Alone or with Family	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Alone	178	49.86
With Family	179	50.14
Total	357	100.00

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 4.8 provides insight into respondents' migration status, indicating whether they migrated to the Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC) alone or with their families. The results show an almost equal distribution: 179 respondents (50.14%) migrated with their families, while 178 (49.86%) migrated alone. This near-equal split highlights the dual nature of migration in AMAC, where both individual- and family-based migration are prevalent.

The slightly higher percentage of family migration suggests that many migrants view AMAC as a stable and accommodating environment suitable for family life. This may reflect the availability of social infrastructure, such as schools, healthcare, and housing that support long-term settlement. It also indicates a trend toward permanent or semi-permanent relocation, rather than temporary or seasonal migration, which is often associated with individuals moving alone.

Conversely, the substantial proportion of those who migrated alone (49.86%) could represent job seekers, students, or those assessing the environment before relocating their families. This group may face unique challenges such as isolation, higher living costs, or difficulty accessing support networks. Overall, the balanced migration status reflects the diverse demographic and socio-economic composition of AMAC's migrant population and has implications for urban policy planning, particularly in housing, social services, and community integration.

Table 4.9: Secondary Migration within Abuja

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	141	39.49
No	216	60.51
Total	357	100.00

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 4.9 presents data on whether respondents have experienced secondary migration within Abuja, meaning they moved from one location within the Federal Capital Territory to another after initially settling. Of the 357 respondents, 141 (39.49%) reported having undergone secondary migration, while the remaining 216 (60.51%) reported not having done so.

The fact that nearly 40% of respondents engaged in secondary migration suggests a significant level of intra-urban mobility within Abuja. This movement could be driven by various factors such as changes in employment, cost of living, housing conditions, or proximity to better services and amenities. Such patterns may place additional pressure on urban infrastructure and planning, as they imply that initial settlement areas may not meet residents' long-term needs.

On the other hand, the majority (60.51%) of respondents remained in their initial place of settlement, indicating stability and satisfaction with their location. This group may benefit from consistent access to services and community integration. Understanding these migration dynamics is important for urban development planners, as secondary migration can affect demand for housing, transportation, and public utilities across different districts of the Abuja Municipal Area Council.

4.3 Impact of Urban Migration on Sustainable Development

Respondents were asked to rate the effects of urban migration on various developmental indicators. A 5-point Likert scale was used (1 = Very Negative, 5 = Very Positive).

Table 4.10: Rating of Migration Impact on Development Indicators

Indicator	Mean Score	Interpretation
Housing availability	2.24	Negative
Access to water/sanitation	2.53	Moderately Negative
Healthcare services	2.69	Neutral
Education facilities	2.89	Neutral to Slightly Positive
Transportation/infrastructure	2.62	Neutral
Waste management	2.38	Negative
Employment opportunities	3.05	Slightly Positive

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 4.10 presents respondents' perceptions of the impact of urban migration on key development indicators in the Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC). The analysis revealed that housing availability received a mean score of 2.24, indicating an adverse effect. This implies that the rapid influx of migrants has strained housing resources, leading to overcrowding, rising rents, and possibly the proliferation of informal settlements. Waste management also received a *negative* perception with a mean score of 2.38, suggesting that urban migration may be overwhelming existing waste disposal systems, thereby contributing to environmental degradation and poor sanitation.

On the other hand, access to water and sanitation was rated *moderately negative* with a mean score of 2.53. This shows that while basic amenities are available, the existing infrastructure may not be sufficient to cater to the growing population driven by migration. Inadequate access to clean water and proper sanitation facilities may increase the risk of communicable diseases and reduce residents' quality of life. Similarly, the rating of 2.62 for *transportation/infrastructure* points to a *neutral* impact, indicating that while the transportation network might be functioning, it is likely operating at or near capacity, with increased traffic congestion and reduced efficiency.

Healthcare services received a *neutral* rating of 2.69, suggesting that urban migration has not significantly enhanced or worsened healthcare delivery in AMAC. However, it could also reflect a balancing effect: new healthcare facilities have been introduced, but demand still outweighs supply. Education facilities, with a mean score of 2.89, show a *neutral to slightly positive* impact, implying that while there is some improvement or expansion in educational infrastructure, it is only marginally keeping pace with the increasing demand from migrant populations.

Interestingly, the most positively rated indicator was employment opportunities, with a mean score of 3.05, indicating a slightly positive rating. This suggests that urban migration has had some beneficial effects on job creation or access to economic activities in AMAC. Migrants might be contributing to the labour force, stimulating local markets, or engaging in entrepreneurial ventures. However, the slight positivity also signals that job creation is not robust enough to fully absorb the influx, underscoring the need for more strategic economic planning to harness migration's development potential.

Table 4.11: Effectiveness of Local Government in Managing Migration

Response Frequency Percentage (%)

Yes	89	24.93
No	189	52.94
Not Sure	79	22.13
Total	357	100.00

Source: Field Survey 2025

The data in Table 4.11 reveal respondents' perceptions of the local government's effectiveness in managing urban migration within the Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC). Of 357 respondents, only 89 (24.93%) believed the government has been effective, suggesting that only a minority perceives positive interventions in infrastructure, public services, or regulation. Conversely, a majority of 189 respondents (52.94%) felt that the government has been ineffective, indicating widespread dissatisfaction likely related to challenges in housing, waste management, traffic, public health, and employment facilitation. Additionally, 79 respondents (22.13%) were uncertain about government effectiveness, possibly reflecting limited awareness, engagement, or transparency regarding migration management policies. Overall, these findings point to a general perception of inadequacy in local government response and highlight a trust gap that could impede collaborative efforts for sustainable urban development. Improving this perception may require participatory governance, enhanced service delivery, and effective communication with residents about migration management initiatives.

4.4 Qualitative Analysis from Open-Ended Responses

The open-ended responses from participants highlighted several key challenges linked to rising urban migration in the Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC). A primary concern was the high cost of rent and the scarcity of affordable housing, which has made decent accommodation increasingly inaccessible for migrants. Overstretched public services, including overcrowded classrooms and under-resourced health facilities, were also reported as significant issues. Infrastructure problems such as poorly maintained roads, traffic congestion, and environmental sanitation challenges, including inadequate waste management and clogged drainage systems, were frequently mentioned. Despite these challenges, respondents acknowledged the benefits of migration, including improved access to education, wider employment opportunities, favourable market conditions for entrepreneurship, and support from

government and NGO programs. To address these issues and promote sustainable development, participants recommended stricter enforcement of urban planning regulations, equitable expansion of social amenities, investment in modern waste management systems, and the creation of employment opportunities for youths and new migrants. These measures are considered essential for improving living conditions, boosting economic productivity, and fostering a sustainable urban environment in AMAC.

4.5 Interview Analysis

Insights from key informant interviews highlighted a significant increase in migration into Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC) over the past decade, driven mainly by the search for employment, better infrastructure, and security from conflict-affected regions. While migration offers improved opportunities for many, it has placed substantial pressure on housing, social services, and infrastructure, including schools, hospitals, roads, and water systems, often exceeding their capacities and reducing service quality. Urban planners noted issues such as unregulated housing, land encroachment, loss of green spaces, and rising congestion, which contribute to inadequate sanitation and heightened health risks, especially in informal settlements. Stakeholders emphasised the need for comprehensive, coordinated, and forward-looking strategies involving local, state, and federal governments, as well as NGOs, with community participation and long-term planning to ensure equitable access to services, sustainable land use, and effective urban management in AMAC.

4.6 DISCUSSION OF RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Analysis of survey responses, interviews, and open-ended feedback indicates that economic and social factors primarily drive urban migration into the Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC). Many individuals and families relocate from other regions of Nigeria in pursuit of better employment opportunities, access to quality education, improved living conditions, and relative safety from insecurity in conflict-affected areas. This pattern reflects broader national trends in which urban centres like AMAC act as hubs for opportunity and stability. Respondents highlighted that migration has provided increased access to markets, vocational training programs, and employment networks, enabling upward mobility and enhanced financial prospects for many households.

Despite these benefits, the growing influx of migrants has placed immense pressure on the city's infrastructure and services, challenging the sustainability of urban development in AMAC. Housing demand far exceeds supply, resulting in higher rents and the expansion of informal settlements. At the same time, roads, schools, healthcare facilities, and water systems struggle to meet the needs of the population. Issues such as traffic congestion, overcrowded classrooms, inadequate medical services, and poor sanitation are increasingly visible. The study also highlights a gap between migration rates and the government's capacity to respond, with insufficient urban planning, weak enforcement of development regulations, and limited coordination among relevant agencies. Overall, while migration has socioeconomic advantages, it exposes weaknesses in urban management, underscoring the need for inclusive, data-driven policies that address population growth, infrastructure, social services, and environmental sustainability to promote equitable and resilient urban development.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of this study indicate that urban migration into the Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC) is a significant demographic trend that profoundly shapes the area's socio-economic and physical landscape. Migration is primarily driven by the pursuit of better employment opportunities, improved living conditions, and access to social services. While these movements have led to some positive outcomes, such as increased economic participation, entrepreneurial activity, and labour market diversification, the rapid pace of migration has exceeded the local government's capacity to manage growth effectively. Essential infrastructure, including housing, water supply, sanitation, healthcare, and transportation, is under severe strain, leading to overcrowding, informal settlements, and environmental degradation. The dissatisfaction expressed by respondents reflects a disconnect between policy

formulation and implementation, underscoring systemic governance challenges, weak enforcement of urban planning regulations, and insufficient resource allocation.

In response to these findings, the study recommends a multifaceted approach to promote sustainable urban development in AMAC. Key measures include addressing the socio-economic drivers of migration by improving rural and peri-urban livelihoods, creating employment opportunities within AMAC, and supporting SMEs and vocational programs (Todaro & Smith, 2020). Enhancing urban infrastructure and public services through investments in affordable housing, transportation, healthcare, education, and sanitation is essential to meet growing demand (Adewale, 2020). Environmental sustainability must be prioritised through stricter regulation, the adoption of renewable energy, waste management, and community engagement in conservation efforts (Ogunjimi & Okunola, 2016). Finally, promoting integrated, participatory, and data-driven urban governance will strengthen planning, accountability, and resilience, ensuring that urban migration becomes a catalyst for inclusive, sustainable development rather than a source of strain on AMAC's resources.

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